

Measurement of the Fracture Toughness of the Metal-Composite Interface in Composite Repair Systems for Steel Pipework

A. A. AL-MASKARI¹, M. ROBINSON¹, A. G. GIBSON¹ AND S. R. FROST²

¹NewRail, Mechanical and Systems Engineering, Newcastle University, UK

²WTR Ltd, Aberdeen, UK

SHORT ABSTRACT

This paper describes the fracture mechanics approach behind the water pressure 'blow-off' test for characterising the failure behaviour of composite repairs on steel tubes. The technique enables the fracture toughness of the metal/composite interface to be determined at the point where failure initiates. Surprisingly the values found for the interfacial fracture toughness are typically an order of magnitude lower than those found in other fracture mechanics tests. A further procedure was therefore developed, in which the water pressure was replaced by a mechanical load from a steel probe. This latter test was carried out with and without water present.

KEY WORDS

Fracture Toughness
Fracture Mechanics
Repair
Tube
Composite-Metal

LONG ABSTRACT:

There has been much recent interest, including the preparation of the first standard, ISO 24817, for the use of composite repair methods for corroded steel tubing. A fracture mechanics methodology has been developed for modelling and understanding the propagation of blistered composite repairs on leaking tubes. This has formed the basis of part of the new standard for the design of composite repairs for steel tubulars. This paper examines the fracture mechanics-based methodology for determining the blistering resistance of repairs in the presence of pressurised water. A flat plate laminate procedure was developed as a more convenient replacement for repaired steel pipe spools to measure values of G_{Ic} relating to the metal-composite interface. This has proved very useful in characterising composite repair systems. The fracture toughness values resulting from this technique are an order of magnitude lower than values obtained via other common types of measurement, which has been attributed to the presence of pressurised water at the site of the repair failure initiation point. To examine this hypothesis, this paper presents fracture toughness measurements using (a) the conventional blow-off method with pressurised water, Figure 1, and (b) similar samples using a mechanical probe to fail the sample with and without water at the failure site Figure 2. Finite Element Analysis has been used to validate and support the fracture mechanics approach used in these tests.

It was found that, for a demonstrator glass/vinyl ester laminate repair system, the interface G_{Ic} value was 199 J/m^2 , when determined using the blow-off test, Figure 1, with pressurised water as the medium. By contrast, G_{Ic} increased by over an order of magnitude to 3422 J/m^2 when tested in air using the probe set-up shown in Figure 2. When tested with un-pressurised water present at the interface, this value decreased a little, to 3060 J/m^2 . This shows that the reason why repair systems of this type show such low fracture toughness values is connected to the presence of pressurised water at the primary repair failure location.

Figure 1 Schematic of the blow-off test.

Figure 2 Schematic of the push-off test